

Component-based machine learning for predicting representative time-series of energy performance in building design

Xia Chen ^a, Manav Mahan Singh ^b, Philipp Geyer ^{a, b}

^a Technische Universität Berlin, Germany, ^b Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium
xia.chen@tu-berlin.de

Abstract. The building industry is benefited by building performance simulation (BPS) for design assistance. Machine learning (ML) has been widely used for quick performance prediction; however, it lacks the flexibility to scale for new designs. By spatially and semantically decomposing the building design into components, this article links the ML approach with the system engineering paradigm of BPS to develop component-based machine learning (CBML). While previous use of CBML focused on point predictions, this study proves that the CBML is able to predict dynamic time-series energy performance for new design cases by deriving a set of reusable model components. We trained and tested the ML model on a dataset of 1000 examples. The objective is to ascertain the ability of the ML model to generalize via different decomposition levels. Hourly energy predictions during the design phase are useful for equipment sizing, controlling peak energy demands, and leveling the load in the networks.

1. Introduction

Digitalization has greatly reshaped the community of architecture (Eastman et al. 2011; Sydora and Stroulia 2020). Simulation for building performance assessment has been applied to the whole life cycle process on a large scale, especially in the design phase (Evins 2013; Østergård et al. 2016; Tian et al. 2018). Regarding the building energy efficiency information such as peak load, cost, etc., performance assessment enables designers, policymakers, and engineers to conduct a wide variety of decision-making and policy implementation toward sustainable energy-efficient buildings (Cao et al. 2016). Among these aspects, one of the important subjects in this domain is building energy prediction at the early stage. Accurately modeling and predicting energy performance provides the foundation for further application (Longo et al. 2019). Accurate predictions of hourly energy consumption will assist in evaluating several design alternatives and operation strategies (Deb et al. 2017a). Especially, the integration of buildings into energy networks exploiting renewable energy and storage capacities requires the prediction of their time-series energy demand.

The development of machine learning (ML) algorithms and cost-efficient computational resources enabled numerous applications for regression, classification, and optimization tasks in an efficient way (Seyedzadeh et al. 2018; Chakraborty and Elzarka 2019). The idea of ML is to feed the data into specific objective functions to capture hidden patterns between input features and outputs by minimizing the error via a recursive training process. The most intuitive approach is training a monolithic model fed with available data from building features and set the target as model output; however, the building features might come from different levels of details. The monolithic approach is incapable of reflecting the internal relationship of variables. In contrast, the component-based machine learning (CBML) approach for energy performance involving the building components relationship into models creates flexibility to integrate domain knowledge (Geyer et al. 2018; Geyer 2009; Geyer and Schlüter 2014; Leblanc et al. 2011). By linking the ML models to general building component structures, the framework offers a possibility to achieve quick support and flexible modeling for energy performance prediction in the early design process. The results show that component-based ML provided a

promising accuracy for a variety of design configurations regarding energy demand (Geyer et al. 2018).

In this paper, we intend to take this approach one step further to prove that the component-based ML approach is capable of capturing the energy performance in time-series prediction tasks. A tree-based ensemble machine learning model is implemented as a basic component. The novelty of including time-series prediction instead of point prediction in this framework is as follow:

- By composition in different component structures, the CBML approach contributes to analyzing energy system characteristics in the building design phase learned from time-series training data with certain energy usage patterns and peaks.
- The CBML approach enables an understanding of thermal behavior and its relationship in predicting energy loads for data-driven models.

This paper develops ML models to predict the building energy consumption in time series with validation of model generalization using the CBML approach. To achieve this objective, the remains of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the methodology of the CBML framework and the ensemble method; Section 3 describes the database and the setup of the training process; Section 4 discusses the results; Section 5 outlines the limitations and future work, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Methodology

2.1 Component-based machine learning for building energy prediction

Developing a building energy prediction ML model for the early design stage is challenging due to evolving shape and structure of the architectural design. A simpler parametrical representation of building envelope by parameters such as shape coefficient (Catalina et al. 2008) and relative compactness (Cheng and Cao 2014) is insufficient to capture its effect and internal flows on the energy performance. Geyer and Singaravel proposed an approach of component-based machine learning (CBML) to overcome this limitation (Geyer and Singaravel 2018). CBML is based on the decomposition of building into components, each representing its thermal behavior. A building consists of thermal zones connected to walls and windows, ground floors, and roofs. This approach is developed to predict energy demand for new shapes by composing the required ML components to represent any design configuration. A model structure comparison between the monolithic and the CBML approaches for time-series prediction is presented in Figure 1.

We intend to train the monolithic approach as the baseline and compare it to the CBML approach in our use case. The data organization is similar to the previous work (Geyer and Singaravel 2018); we kept the same structure of the data and intermediate value features (heat flow) yet varied each feature's value in a range to represent different building design schemes. The general input building characteristic, output target, and feature engineering used in both approaches are identical. In the CBML approach, we trained building components separately by applying intermediate value as outputs and aggregate for further target output prediction. In the end, the general accuracy of both approaches is compared in average energy performance in time-series format.

Figure 1 System used for (a) CBML and (b) monolithic ML

2.2 Benchmark: Monolithic ML

In this study, we chose the monolithic ML model approach as a benchmark, which refers to using a single ML model to predict the building's heating and cooling loads. Contrary to the CBML approach, this approach relies on using all relevant design parameters to predict thermal energy loads; hence, compared to CBML, it has less flexibility to be applied for new design cases. Normally, it requires parameters in full detail, making it less practical in the early design phase.

2.3 ML algorithm: LightGBM

A large number of literature reviews (Amasyali and El-Gohary 2018; Machairas et al. 2014; Zhao and Magoulès 2012) indicates that the current mainstream machine learning algorithms in the BPS community are mainly: Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Random Forest (RF), Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Gaussian Processes (GP), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) (Amasyali and El-Gohary 2018; Deb et al. 2017b; Somu et al. 2020). In addition to the above methods, ensemble methods in both real-world competitions, such as Kaggle¹ and building performance forecasting research (Chakraborty and Elzarka 2019), have been reported

¹ Online survey available: <https://www.kaggle.com/kaggle-survey-2020>

with an advance in accuracy. In particular, the category of Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT) (Friedman 2001) has been applied widely and excelled in practice.

In our use case, instead of only using continuous time-series data, building characteristics and discrete features also play an important role in integrating domain knowledge into the prediction. GBDT algorithms are developed under the concept of boosting (Freund et al. 1999), compared with Long short-term memory (LSTM) and Recurrent neural network (RNN), boosting technic in such cases shows benefit in generalization by sequentially random sampling and mixing categorical, numerical feature types with historical observations of the target for training. Hence, in our paper, we use GBDT as the ML method to predict the time-series data. Since the dataset we use contains different shapes of buildings, we expand the sparse discrete building features into the same length as time-based input. In this paper, we chose an efficient algorithm - Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) as our ML model. LightGBM implements a highly optimized histogram-based decision tree learning algorithm, which yields great advantages in efficiency and memory consumption. Further insight and an open-source implementation in detail are available in the mentioned reference (Guolin Ke et al.).

3. Case study

3.1 Case study details

This study uses a typical medium-size office building in Munich as a test example. An EnergyPlus model is used to simulate its energy performance. This EnergyPlus model is validated against the yearly energy consumption of the real building. The validation results are available on Mendeley datasets (Singh 2021). The relevant design parameters are modified for creating training and test datasets. The design parameters mentioned in Table 1 are considered in this study to develop datasets. The building shape of training data and test data are shown in Figure 2. The test data has random building shapes to validate that the trained ML components are reusable for new design cases. The random building shapes are generated by arranging squares of varying dimensions. We used the EnergyPlus model to generate time-series energy performance for all the dimension schemes individually. The floor area per floor for random shapes is in the range of 200 to 800 sqm.

Figure 2 Representation of building shape used for training and test data

Table 1. Design parameters for training and testing

Parameters	Unit	Min	Max	Parameters	Unit	Min	Max
Length	m	12	30	Heat Capacity (Slab)	kJ/m ³ K	0.8	1.0
Width		12	30	Window-to-Wall Ratio	-	0.1	0.5
Floor Height		3.0	4.0	Internal Mass	kJ/m ²	60	120
No. of Floors	-	2	4	Air Permeability	m ³ /h·m ²	6	9
Orientation	°	0	90	Operating Hours	h	10	12
u value (Wall)	W/m ² K	0.15	0.25	Occupant Load	m ² /Person	16	24
u value (Ground Floor)		0.15	0.25	Light Heat Load	W/m ²	6	10
u value (Roof)		0.15	0.25	Equipment Heat Load		10	14
u value (Window)		0.7	1.0	Heating COP	-	2.5	4.5
u value (Internal Floor)		0.4	0.6	Cooling COP		2.5	4.5
g value	-	0.3	0.6	Boiler Efficiency		0.92	0.98

This study makes hourly energy prediction for two typical and two extreme weather conditions to cover a range of representative prediction conditions. Based on the weather information, the days mentioned in Table 2 have been selected to study the proposed approach. These days represent typical weather conditions for calculating the peak energy demand and sizing the energy system.

Table 2. Days selected for hourly energy prediction

Interval	Days	Interval	Days
Winter typical	January 05 – January 17	Summer typical	July 12 – July 24
Winter extreme	February 09 – February 21	Summer extreme	July 19 – July 31

3.2 Machine learning strategy

Four data categories exist in our dataset: weather, time, building features, and target outputs. As time-series data are required for all categories, we expand the discrete features in Design parameters for training and testing to time-series data by repetition. By this transformation, all input features are available in time-series format. As the ensemble tree-based algorithm's split finding mechanism is insensitive to the value range, data scaling is not required (Marsland 2015). In this research, we only decomposed and engineered the cyclical time features such as the month, week, day, etc., as shown in Table 3. Especially, we used the Boolean value to represent whether the day is weekend or workday to enhance the ML model's recognition of energy usage patterns.

Table 3. Decomposition of time features

Name	Definition	Name	Definition
<i>tm_d</i>	Day of month	<i>tm_wm</i>	Week of month
<i>tm_w</i>	Week of year	<i>tm_dw</i>	Day of week
<i>tm_m</i>	Month	<i>tm_w_end</i>	If is weekend

As for hyperparameters' optimization, we kept the default setting of most hyperparameters² in LightGBM but fine-tuned the iteration round to prevent model underfitting or overfitting. The cross-validation as hyperparameter tuning technique was used for the best iteration identification. More specifically, a 3-fold cross-validation method was applied to the training process with 300 early stopping epochs, which means the training dataset is equally split into

² Default setting of hyperparameters is available on LightGBM 3.2.1.99 documentation (2021): <https://lightgbm.readthedocs.io/en/latest/Parameters.html?highlight=default>

three subsets, the subsets are repeatedly fed in a model using combinations of two sub-training and one sub-validation set, and the error from each validation was averaged. The averaged error was under supervised during the cross-validation training process until it stops dropping for 300 iterations, then the best iteration rounds are confirmed.

The dataset is split into two independent parts as training and test set. The training set contains a thousand buildings with corresponding components, while in the test set, five hundred buildings of different shapes. We trained all levels of components independently, then used the CBML approach by taking the predicted output of component-level, integrated according to the different composition of zone-levels, further into building-level components to predict the target load, as shown in Figure 1. At the same time, we also trained monolithic ML models for zone-level and building-level as a benchmark. The target periods and outputs are *Heating Load: Winter typical*, *Heating Load: Winter extreme*, *Cooling Load: Summer typical*, and *Cooling Load: Summer extreme*.

4. Results

We took the monolithic ML at the building level as the baseline. The detailed results of components and monolithic MLs in terms of accuracy are available in Table 4. Both accuracy results are concluded by compared with the EnergyPlus model output. To cover all three-level CBML architecture, we also show the results of the monolithic model at zone-level for comparison. Except the *CBML building* is conducted by the CBML approach, the rest rows in Table 4 show results of the monolithic model. In general, both approaches present novel performance in time-series prediction in BPS. The accuracy of CBML approaches in all four scenarios degrades only slightly compared to direct prediction, which is impressive by given the fact that: 1. the buildings in the test set are compositionally different from the training set and 2. It requires the variable transfer among the different model components.

Table 4. Accuracy of ML components (R^2 values)

Component	Heating Load		Cooling Load	
	Winter Typical	Winter Extreme	Summer Typical	Summer Extreme
Ground floor	0.9252	0.8941	0.9065	0.8797
Infiltration	0.9743	0.9835	0.9777	0.9826
Roof	0.9462	0.9542	0.9127	0.8967
Wall & Window	0.9726	0.9770	0.9826	0.9823
Zone*	0.9889	0.9877	0.9669	0.9791
Building*	0.9141	0.9731	0.9700	0.9746
CBML Building	0.9274	0.9217	0.9422	0.9597

* using monolithic ML

If we compare the performance of components closely in Table 4, it is worth noting that components-level performs better at predicting energy demand for infiltration and walls but less accurate for ground floor and roof. The reason might be as follows: In addition to more available features in infiltration and Wall & Window components as inputs, roof and floor normally have a large area; A bigger area brings more uncertainties in heat flow behavior for forecasting; furthermore, due to the horizontal orientation of the roof and floor, they show less sensitiveness to external weather data. Compared to the monolithic model, such a decomposition with a separation reasoning process is only available in the CBML approach, contributing to a better model explainability.

Figure 3 visualizes the performance of energy demand prediction in four different periods. We rendered an extra relative error plot under each prediction to avoid read difficulty due to curves'

close overlap. We remove outlier pikes (larger than 1) in the error plot for demonstration purposes when the load is zero. The CBML approach shows a better coverage at peak load in the summer period. Specifically, the visualization shows that inaccurate parts (the absolute value of relative error larger than 0.2) normally appear at the lower part of the load (around 0), contributing the most to accuracy degradation. A common solution for this problem is introducing the intermittent forecasting method to alleviate it in future research. The most important fact is that the CBML approach is capable of capturing the peak load and usage patterns for non-existent buildings, achieve comparable performance as the direct ML approach.

Figure 3 Performance visualization of energy demand prediction with relative error plots

5. Discussion

This paper demonstrated the feasibility of time-series prediction by the CBML approach has been by implementing the tree-based ensemble algorithm for energy demand prediction based on a decomposition scheme for BPS. The hourly CBML prediction has been validated by simulation results against the monolithic ML approach. It is worth pointing out that in Figure 4, the CBML prediction result shows fluctuation at lower load, even negative values. If we consider eliminating the negative value manually, the general performance will be further enhanced. Compared to monolithic ML prediction, it shows the following advantages: (1) CBML covers a range of configurations not included in the training data. The direct ML approach is less likely to build in practice due to the data collection difficulties; Due to the separate component training process, the CBML approach has the flexibility to predict under a certain level of incomplete inputs, which as an essential feature is needed, especially in the early design phase; (2) The CBML approaches provide the possibility to predict the peak load and usage patterns for different shapes of non-existent buildings in the design phase. In practice, they are important indicators for building designers in scheme evaluation, e.g., plant and system dimensioning. (3) Building designers and engineers can access inter-component results to understand why a design performs well or badly. After the deployment, such an extra energy performance time-series data also contributes to model calibration for engineers in simulation; (4) The components integrate seamlessly in digital modeling as performed in BIM, which means fewer efforts are required for the model deployment in real-world scenarios. (5) CBML building components are reusable in different cases once they achieve a certain level of generalization by fed-in enough data. A huge potential to build up a standardized building energy performance library with a limited number of components. Such a library brings the opportunity for fast modelling in the building design assistance.

The accuracy of the model is highly dependent on the data input. As the current model is trained on the synthetic data generated by the energy simulation tool, the study does not address the gap between simulation and actual energy demand. The next step in the component-based ML approach's research is further accuracy validation of error propagation and training under real data, which contains more noise and uncertainty. In addition, a detailed classification of building types due to different energy usage pattern settings needs to be performed, such as for residential buildings, commercial buildings, etc. This may lead to bias in the final prediction results of real cases.

6. Conclusion

To sum up, we incorporated time-series prediction in component-based ML for modeling building performance. The approach provides better generalization than monolithic ML as it allows the use of components assembled in different configurations as required by design. The generalization has been successfully demonstrated because CBML predicts load behavior under representative weather conditions for design configurations not included in the training data. The accuracy of the predictions does not degrade significantly during variables transfer among components. This result demonstrates that the component-based approach owns the transferable flexibility to predict the energy performance of non-existent buildings. This method and its additional information provide vital support in the building early design phase. Especially, the quick and accurate prediction of time-series with peaks and patterns, the integration in digital design and modeling of buildings, and the explainability by inter-component information form important benefits. Such abilities enable machine assistance for building design support with considerable benefit for design process efficiency and solutions.

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